

FEATURES OF INTERTEXTUAL HEADLINES IN NEWSPAPER TEXTS

Musaev Bek Mustafaevich

teacher of the department of Russian philology
Ferghana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8119694>

Annotation: the article deals with the linguistic foundations of creating headings using intertextual elements as an example. The main attention is focused on the ways of introducing intertext and its functional features.

Key words: intertextuality, quotation, reminiscence, context, title, newspaper text, two-dimensionality.

The relevance of the study is due to the need for a comprehensive study of the intertextual elements that function in the texts of modern media, and is explained by the importance of identifying trends in the selection and involvement of reminiscences in the construction of newspaper headlines. And also by the fact that quite complex reminiscences are often found in newspaper texts. The problem of intertext, reminiscence, citation, "foreign" word in "one's own" is currently one of the most popular, although it began to be developed relatively recently.

Intertextuality creates a vertical context that complicates the speech work of a journalist, giving rise to two-dimensionality or multidimensionality, the "included text" serves the purposes of a language game of various kinds: it contributes to the poeticization of the text, creates a poetic hint, subtext, creates a riddle, creates an ironic, sarcastic, grotesque, tragic or other sound. It contributes to the hierarchization of meaning, "the selection of the semantic dominant" [1], gives the everyday phrase the meaning of an allegory - political, poetic, philosophical or any other.

Citation has become one of the most striking features of modern journalism, which uses such intertextuality techniques as allusion, reminiscence, allusion, quotation, etc. This feature comes through most actively in the headlines, which are the strongest position of the newspaper text.

The specificity of the title is manifested in the fact that, along with the beginning and ending, it refers to the compositional elements of the text that attract increased attention when you first get acquainted with the publication. Making a headline easy to read, informative, and at the same time intriguing is one of the most difficult tasks of a journalist. To create such a title, the authors of articles often resort to the use of so-called precedent texts. Modern culture is not prone to text generation, but is prone to the use of artistic quotation, namely, the use of author's quotations and oral folk art (proverbs, sayings and lines from songs). But intertextuality is successful when the effect of "recognition" of the encoded meaning occurs. Otherwise, a communication failure occurs. That is, the quoted texts should be precedent, well known to a wide audience, since the language of mass communication is focused on mass consciousness. But such an orientation of the media towards a mass audience leads to the replication of once found methods of intertextuality: "Peculiarities of

national life”, “Peculiarities of national boxing” (film “Peculiarities of the national hunt”), “Man does not live by cheese alone”, “Man does not live by salt alone” etc. Thus, clichés are obtained that fit into speech formulas: “peculiarities of the national ..” or “not ... a single person lives”, etc., where instead of ... you can substitute any thematic lexeme necessary for the journalist, and intertextuality from an expressive means of journalism turns into a faceless stamp.

The choice and implementation of the intertext in the text should be determined by at least two factors: the function that the intertextual element will perform in the publication, and the background knowledge of the target audience of the publication. The use of references to literary sources in journalistic materials is in many cases very appropriate and expedient, since, firstly, they can sometimes allow the author to express what is directly, without resorting to literary parallels, comparisons, analogies, to express more precisely, more clearly. Secondly, the introduction of intertextual elements into the text helps the reader to better navigate the message of the author. Let's look at examples:

“The meeting continues, gentlemen” (Our newspaper, 08/13/2015), cf.: “The ice has broken, gentlemen of the jury. The meeting continues! (I. Ilf, E. Petrov "12 chairs"). In the given example, reminiscences are connected with the text by the fact that there is an artistic association, irony, a hint at the image of Ostap Bender during the elections to deputies [2].

“So as not to disappear one by one” (Our newspaper, 02/16/2017) cf.: “Let's join hands, friends, / So as not to disappear one by one” (B. Okudzhava). The article is devoted to the problems of campaigning for the unification of personal subsidiary farms into cooperatives, to strengthen the importance of unity, the lines of B. Okudzhava are used.

“I would go to the leaders!” (Kostanay news, 06/09/2016), cf.: “I would go to pilots, let them teach me” - lines from V. Mayakovsky's poem illustrate the topic of the article. This is a rally of young talents, which was attended by more than a hundred activists, they honed their organizational and communication skills under the guidance of senior mentors.

“Hour of the Bull” (Kostanay News, 07/12/2016) - a story about breeding bulls on the farm - an allusion to the title of the novel by Ivan Antonovich Efremov “The Hour of the Bull”, hinting at a long wait for the result and the problems associated with it [3].

“Little dramas of the big hippodrome” (Kostanay News, 06/03/2015). The function of intertext in an article about the dramatic opening of the equestrian season at the Argamak hippodrome in the village of Zarechny is to evoke associations with the name of the performance of the Satire Theater "Little Comedies of the Big House" and A. S. Pushkin's work "Little Tragedies" in order to attract attention to the difficulties experienced by both people and horses on the hippodrome.

“The Salt of the Karasu Land” (Kostanay News, 08/06/2015) is a reminiscence to the title of Georgy Markov's book “The Salt of the Earth” is intended to enhance the effect of the author's impression of the inhabitants of the Karasu village, who “wage a constant struggle and win”, growing flowers and trees on saline soils. In addition, there is a clash of two meanings in the title, which enhances the influencing effect.

“A white hare, not an ugly duckling and 200 quails” (Kostanay news, 05/28/2016) - the title of an article about the large poultry farm of Yerbolat Kapyshev evokes the title of the fairy tale by G. Andersen “The Ugly Duckling”, in connection with which there are associations with the significance of birds, grown on private farms.

The title "City that exists" (Kostanay news 02/18/2015) represents an artistic association for the lines of I. Kornelyuk's song "I see a city that does not exist in the distance ..." and reminds readers that the city of Arkalyk in the Kostanay region is still alive, but emphasizes problems of its development.

"Desires for a goldfish" (Kostanay news, 12/18/2014). An intertext containing an artistic image of a wish-fulfilling fish from A.S. Pushkin "The Tale of the Fisherman and the Fish", draws attention to an article about the work of the rehabilitation department for children with cerebral palsy and dreaming of healing.

"There, on the snow-covered paths..." (Kostanay news, 01/17/2017). And again, an intertextual reference to the artistic image from the poem "There, on unseen paths, traces of unseen animals" by A.S. Pushkin illustrates the state of access roads to the village of Zhambyl, Karasu district, Kostanay region. "Time to collect stones" (Kostanay news, 11/15/2016). Philosophical mood is caused by the lines "Time to scatter stones, and time to collect stones; a time to hug, and a time to avoid hugs" (Ecclesiastes, chapter 3), which were quoted by the author of an article about the problems of house repair in connection with the reform of housing and communal services.

The intertextual heading "Planet of Christmas Trees" (Kostanay News, 12/17/2015) refers to the fairy tale "Planet of Christmas Trees" by Gianni Rodari, about a boy who ended up on a utopian planet, where every day is New Year, Christmas trees grow on the streets along with decorations, instead of rain - mints and evokes artistic associations among readers. The article deals with Christmas trees, which are installed in each district of the Kostanay region a month before the holiday [4].

"To sleep peacefully for a whole year" ("In Kostanay, innovations in the Tax Code will be explained at seminars" - Our newspaper, 01/05/2017) - probably the intertext of the song "Beloved city can sleep peacefully" and the expression "Paid taxes - and sleep peacefully" , which performs the function of social advertising. The contamination of intertextual elements reflects the main idea of the article about the need to comply with the requirements of the Tax Code.

"We are all a little monkeys" (Kostanay news, 12/31/2015). The artistic image of the symbol of 2015 (monkey) evokes associations among readers with the lines of V. Mayakovsky's poem "A good attitude towards horses": "Baby, we are all a little bit of a horse, each of us is a horse in his own way ...", which is a reflection of the author's commitment theory of the origin of life on Earth by Charles Darwin, and also performs an advertising function [5].

"Affordable". How much is in this word..." (Kostanayskiye Novosti, 10/25/2014), cf.: "Moscow... how much has merged in this sound for the Russian heart!" (A. S. Pushkin, "Eugene Onegin"). Intertext helps to increase the importance of affordable housing for everyone interested in purchasing it.

Often headings use intertextual reminiscences to phraseological units, proverbs:

"Another "shooting at sparrows"" (Our newspaper, 2017, January 12) - the phraseological unit "shoot sparrows from a cannon" illustrates the situation when, even before the start of the amendments to the legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan regulating internal migration of the population, they unfolded on social networks sharp criticism.

“Do not “wash your hands...” (Kostanay news, 11/17/2016). The author, using the particle “not” in the title, gives the text of the article the opposite meaning to the phraseological unit “I wash my hands”, believing that “practice shows that there is always an opportunity to defend one's rights. You just have to decide.” In the presented context, the desire of the journalist to draw attention to the problem and encourage them to fight for their rights is realized.

“The work of the master...” (Kostanay news, 09/03/2015) a reference to the proverb: “The work of the master is afraid.” An article about the work of Zhanna Tashmukanova in making dolls, including the high quality of their performance, justifies the ambiguous nature of the intertextual title.

“The leash for the flood turned out to be cheap” (Our newspaper, 05/04/2017). The intertextual reference to the phrase “Keep on a short leash” in the title reveals the text of the article about the natural disaster in the Kostanay region, which could not be prevented. “The forest is guarded, the chips fly” (Kostanay news, 03/26/2015) - “They cut the forest - the chips fly” - a proverb, a reminiscence to which is used to tell about the work of the Mendykarinsky huntsman.

“How they look into the water” (Kostanay News, 07/02/2015). Phraseologism “Looking into the water” artistically represents the image of rescue divers.

“When the case is one big pipe” (Kostanay news, 02/16/2016) phraseological unit “The case is a pipe (tobacco)”. The text of the article is about the unsatisfactory work of the municipal water canal in the city of Rudny [6].

Songs often quoted in newspaper headlines are:

“At a nameless height” (Kostanay news, 07/28/2016). “There is a unique structure in our region. One of the highest in the world of its kind. But at the same time, there is not a word about him in encyclopedias, the Internet” - a reminiscence in the headline to the lines “Near an unfamiliar village, at an unnamed height” by M. Matusovsky helps to draw attention to the problems of a television and radio mast.

“We are ours, we will build a new house,” reads the title of the article (Kostanay News, 08/01/2015) - “Modern technologies not only simplify and reduce the cost of the production process, but also make it interesting and exciting.” A reminiscence to the lines of the “Internationale” by E. Pottier in the translation of A. Kotz is used: “We are ours, we will build a new world, - Who was nothing, he will become everything”, emphasizing the significant opportunities provided in the process of using innovations.

Thus, in the work we have identified the main function of the intertext in order to draw attention to the problem, express the attitude, highlight the leading thought. In accordance with the classification of E.A. Zemskaya, examining the citation in the headlines of modern newspapers, we identified the following types of precedent texts included in the headlines [2, p. 159-167]: 1) poetic lines (in examples 1, 9, etc.); 2) prose quotes (6); 3) lines from famous songs (28-35); 4) titles of works of art (4, 5, etc.); 5) titles of domestic and foreign films (9); 6) proverbs, sayings and popular expressions (22-27); 7) current expressions of the era of socialism (31); 8) paraphrases of Holy Scripture (16). According to the data obtained as a result of the analysis of the material, the intertext in the headlines of the newspapers “Kostanay News”, “Nasha Gazeta” for the period 2014-2017 is carried out with the help of such types of reminiscences as: mention, citation, transformed quotation, allusion.

Newspapers are characterized by three identical methods of playing with precedent text in the headline: substitution, truncation, adding a component.

Exploring this topic, we drew attention to the fact that reminiscences in their pure form in the headlines of journalistic texts are quite rare. Perhaps this is due to the insufficiently high level of knowledge of the cultural and literary and artistic layers of the past by the modern reader. Realizing this, journalists probably avoid such images and intertexts, for the perception of which the average statistical education may not be enough. Another reason, perhaps, lies in the high speeds of information exchange, which puts a temporary barrier on the way of mastering large amounts of information: readers do not have enough time for thoughtful mastering, involving in-depth knowledge, memory resources, past experience.

The process of reproduction in media texts of texts already existing in the language involves cognitive and mental efforts aimed at extracting language units from memory. This process must be considered in a broad communicative context - as the formation of an ideal content, accompanied by a search for a language form assigned to it and culminating in the "linking" of this content with the desired form.

Intertext, as a rule, is a multi-word complex, therefore, it requires great mental effort to retrieve from memory. Reproduction of intertext in media publications is based on various mental operations - the actual reproduction and recall. Reproduction itself is the re-creation of material in memory without relying on perception. Such reproduction is the basis of the bulk of the actualizations of the intertext - their extraction from memory and inclusion in the statement. In the processes of remembering and recalling language units, their separate features appear on the "surface" of memory - structural and meaningful [7].

Understanding the reproducibility of intertext as a reconstruction according to some formal and content features underlies different types of structural and semantic transformations of precedent texts in media materials. The mechanism of intertext involvement in a newly created utterance requires special design in accordance with its intended position in the syntactic scheme and, most importantly, its coordination with the semantic concept of the entire utterance being formed.

Intertextual meaning, being realized in the context, undergoes various transformations, determined not only by the specifics of the designated objects, phenomena, situations of extralinguistic reality, but also by the intention of the addresser, as well as by the strategy or plan of speech behavior chosen by him to implement this intention. This strategy depends on the specific contextual and situational conditions of speech, as well as on the social, personal and psychophysical properties of the addressee. In other words, the processes of actualization of the intertext are accompanied by the "adjustment" of their semantics and structure to the context, thus achieving unity in the structural-semantic relation of the context and intertext. It is the context that adapts the meanings to the information they carry, actualizing or reducing the information brought by the meaning of the reference. Thus, the role of the context in shaping the perception of information and suggestion is enormous, because the intertext "causes the development of internal changes in the perception of the surrounding world, as a result, other expectations and principles are developed and determined, the potential for assimilation of new information increases".

References:

1. Avetisyan N.G. The language of the media as a factor in the development of the language // Bulletin of Moscow State University. Ser. 19. Linguistics and intercultural communication. - M., 2002. - No. 4 - S.80-86.
2. Akishina A. A. The structure of the whole text. M., 1979. - 78 p.
3. Alpatov V.M. Issues of linguistics in the works of M.M. Bakhtin 40 of the 60s // Questions of Linguistics. - M., 2001. No. 6. - S. 16-23.
4. Andreev V.V., Petrova T.A. On two trends in the development of the newspaper language // Mass media: history and modernity. Cheboksary, 1999. - S. 241-253.
5. Bessonov V.A. Newspaper headline. L., 1958. - 63 p.
6. Bogdanov N.G., Vyazemsky B.A. Journalist's Handbook. L., 1971. -688 p.
7. Bogoslovskaya O.I., Poltavskaya E.A. On the problem of correlation between newspaper headline and genre // Functional stylistics: theory of styles and their language implementation. Perm, 1986.-S. 111-118.
8. Vakurov V.N. Stylistics of newspaper genres. M., 1978. - 183 p.
9. Vasilyeva A.N. Newspaper and journalistic style of speech: a course of lectures on the style of the Russian language. M., 1982. - 239 p.
10. Lazareva E.A. The title and the beginning of the newspaper text // The word in systemic relations at different levels of the language. M., 1989. - S. 121-131.
11. Lukanina M.V. Newspaper text through the prism of communication theory // Bulletin of Moscow State University. Ser. 19. Linguistics and intercultural communication. -M., 2003.- №2.- S. 123-133.